

Awareness and expectation of industrial engineering students on competences required toward Industrial revolution 4.0

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Abstract

Industrial revolution 4.0 has already changed the way industrial engineers work. Several skills needed to support Industrial 4.0 technology, such as data analytics and industrial automation, have been shifting from an optional skill to a minimum required skill. In this paper, the competences required by industry for the future workforce were addressed in a survey for industrial engineering students at Thammasat University. Students were asked to evaluate their current competence levels and to define their expected competence levels of the required skills. The result reveals that the competence levels increase significantly from first-year students to fourth-year students. However, there appear to be gaps between current competence levels of the fourth-year students and industry needs. It is also interesting to note that the expected competence levels from industry needs and from students' expectation, regardless of enrolled year, is significantly indifferent.

Keywords: Industrial 4.0; Industrial Engineering; Engineering Education; Curriculum Development.

1 Introduction

As many of us are aware, the industrial revolution 4.0 (I4.0) has now become a global megatrend. In this new industrial revolution, machines, computers, and robots will be performing and will be replacing many of human jobs. The university needs to reform the way of teaching, as well as, to redesign the curriculum, so that graduates can lead the adoption of Industrial 4.0 technology strongly. In the context of Thailand industry, there are studies on the awareness and strategic planning for handling changes on I4.0 of companies in Thailand (Korkueasuebsai, 2019; Pingwong, 2019; Rohitratana and Kumpirarusk, 2019). However, there is only one on-going research in Thailand focused on the development of curriculum for preparing the workforce to tackle the I4.0 revolution. (MSIE4.0 project, 2020)

This study aims to identify the perception of industrial engineering (IE) students on the competences needed from industry under the context of Industry revolution 4.0 (I4.0). This crucial information will be used to redesign the curriculum to meet industry needs. The survey was focused on the students from the bachelor degree program in industrial Engineering at Thammasat University (TU), Thailand, which was established in 1990. The department offers programs in industrial engineering for bachelor degree (B.IE), master degree (M.IE), and doctoral degree. There are currently 226 undergraduate students and 98 graduate students enrolled in all programs. The current curriculum of bachelor degree is the version of the academic year 2018-2023. It is a requirement from the government that a curriculum must be revised every five years or less. Although the concept of I4.0 has been incorporated in the current curriculum, the insights on a specific set of competences needed from industry point-of-view has not yet been considered in the curriculum revision before.

According to the report published on the MSIE4.0 project website regarding what competences that industry needs, there are 32 competences that industrial engineers should equip after completing the master degree in industrial engineering. The competences are defined based on three main technologies of I4.0, which are big data, sensor, and mobile device. These technologies were then used to identify the list of competences required on three application areas, including production technology, product development and IT-based integrated system. The report suggests that the most important outcome for MSIE graduates is to be able to provide

better solutions for various industry practical problems using big data technology in the domain of production technology, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Relative importance of main technologies and main domains of applications for MSIE students (MSIE4.0 Project, 2020)

Moreover, the gaps between industry needs versus the corresponding competences from the current curriculum offered in the university in Thailand are also measured, as presented in Figure 2. It is interesting to note that the gap between these two perspectives is considerably large on most competences. Thus, the modification of the current M.IE curriculum in Thailand is mandatory.

Figure 2. Gap analysis of competence level from industry needs (MSIE4.0 Project, 2020)

The findings from MSIE4.0 project was fruitful as a guideline for developing the IE curriculum in master degree level based on industry needs. However, the perspective from B.IE students on their current competence level and the expected competences level has not been studied under the I4.0 requirement on the IE competences. Besides, it would be better that B.IE graduates could have the same set of competences as equipped on M.IE graduates, although the competence levels would be different. As such, this study was done in two phases to find out the missing competences as mentioned by industry. In the first phase, we analysed the B.IE curriculum that is currently offered at TU. The aim of this phase is to identify the difference between the set of competences needed from industry on I4.0 and the set of competences provided in the current B.IE curriculum. In the second phase, the survey of B.IE students and the data analysis were conducted to obtain the awareness of students on the competence levels. The result was discussed in three views. These include the gap between current competence levels and expected levels of B.IE students, the trend of students' competence level changed after completing each academic year, and the similarity of industry expectation and B.IE students' expectation on the competence level. The summary of this study is then reported in the sections below.

2 Analysis of current B.IE curriculum

The current curriculum of B.IE offered at Thammasat University is the version of academic year 2018-2022. We also compared the list of competences with the previous version of the B.IE curriculum, the version of academic year 2013-2017. The analysis was done by investigating the course description and course outlines from all courses defined in the curriculum. The competences were then extracted to match the list of industry needs from MSIE4.0 report. In summary, the latest version of the B.IE curriculum currently offered at TU can respond to 20 competences required by Industry 4.0, as depicted in Figure 3. These competences were then used to develop the questionnaire in the next phase.

Figure 3. Summary of competences provided in the current B.IE curriculum at TU

3 Methodology

The questionnaire was developed based on the list of competences provided by the current curriculum, see Section 2. Based on Bloom's taxonomy (Bloom et al, 1984), students were asked to evaluate their current competence levels. Competence levels are detailed in Table 1. After that, they were asked whether they want to increase their competence level or not. In the case that students want to increase their competence level, they have to define the expected level on each competence. Using questionnaire as a tool to assess student's awareness is a well-known method and is widely used in several aspects, such as the study presented in Delgado (2008), Yacob et al. (2012), and Root and McKay (2014).

The participants are the entire B.IE students at TU who were asked to complete the questionnaire after the midterm exam of the second semester, i.e. Spring semester, of the academic year 2019. There was 100% of the questionnaire returned to us. After the validation of data, we found that there are 186 answers qualified for the analysis, which is approximately 85% of the total number of enrolled B.IE students.

The data was analyzed using statistical methods based on the normal distribution assumption for the mean and standard deviation of samples. The hypothesis testing on the difference of the mean competence level was conducted using the analysis of variance for one-factor. The Tukey's HSD test method is then used for the multiple comparison procedure on the mean of competence level. See details and formula of the statistical analysis in (Walpole et al, 1994). The analysis was done in Minitab(R) software.

The level of competence used in this study is based on the Bloom's Taxonomy. There are five levels of competences, which are understand, apply, analyze, evaluate, and create. Note that from the graph in Figure 2, the level of competence from MSIE4.0 project report ranges from 1 to 5. In this study, since the survey is focused on undergraduate students, it is possible that students may not have heard about the advanced name of competences, especially for the first-year students. Thus, the competence level in this study ranges from 0 to 7 as explained in Table1. After the survey, data was collected and analyzed using the statistical software, Minitab(R). The average of competence levels was categorized according to the criteria in Table1.

Table1. Explanation of competence level used in questionnaire

Bloom's Taxonomy	Competence level used in MSIE4.0	Competence level used in study	Competence level used in this study	Range of average value from survey
Unknown	0	0	0	0.00 - 0.49
Know	-	1	1	0.50 – 1.49
Remember	-	2	2	1.50 – 2.49
Understand	1	3	3	2.50 – 3.49
Apply	2	4	4	3.50 – 4.49
Analyze	3	5	5	4.50 – 5.49
Evaluate	4	6	6	5.50 – 6.49
Create	5	7	7	6.50- 7.00

4 Analysis of students' awareness and expectation

In this study, the competence level of students was surveyed in three aspects, the current competence level from student's self-evaluation, the expected competence level from student's view, and the expected competence level from industry. The average trend of current student skill level changing at each stage of the academic year and distance between skill levels for each Industry 4.0 requirement were likewise noted, as well as current undergraduate skill level through the questionnaire.

The study can be concluded as follows. For student competence levels as presented in Figure 5, most competence levels seem to be increased after completing each academic year. The lines in the graph represent 20 competences provided in the current curriculum from Figure 3. From Figure 6, the gaps between expected competence level and current competence level of students after completing the bachelor's degree program was quantified. The survey reveals that, on average, the expectation from industry and students on the level of competences are on the same level, that is the analyzed level. See definition in Section 3.2. However, the average competence levels of students are on the apply level. Thus, there are gaps between the current competence level and the expected competence level from either student's expectation and industrial expectation. These findings can offer suggestions for revising academic curricula to meet the needs of Industry 4.0.

Figure 5. Summary of average competence level of students from first-year to fourth-year

Figure 6. Summary of expected level of competences from industry (solid line), student's expectation on average (dashed line), and expected level from student in each year.

5 Conclusion

The main objectives and benefits of this research is to learn about the perceptions and expectations of the skill level that the industry requires under the context of Industry 4.0 in order to be a way to adjust the curriculum to meet the needs of today's industry. Results from the analysis of current curriculum suggest the decisive information that can be used for the curriculum revision. A set of questionnaires was developed to understand the expectation of students toward the competences required by industry. The expectations from students and industry are on the same level, yet the perception of students on their own competences are lower than their expectations. However, the study uses a survey to measure the perception of students on the competence level they have already had, the result might be different if another method were used, such as using a test to measure the competences level.

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